

ISOTHERM AND THERMODYNAMICS STUDIES FOR ADSORPTION OF DISSOLVED SOLID PARTICLES ON COW BONE GRANULE

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ABSTRACT

Cow bone was studied for the removal of dissolved solid particles in coal effluent. Batch adsorption experiments were carried out as a function of concentration of dissolved particles, adsorbent dosage and contact time. Particle removal rate was observed to increase with time, and percentage removal was highest (>60%) at the maximum adsorbent dosage (1.0g). The experimental results were analyzed using Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms to access the fitness of the experimental data. The favourability parameters - $1/n$ (for Freundlich model) and R_L (for Langmuir model) were 0.4274 and 0.026 respectively, indicating a favourable adsorption process; smaller value of $1/n$ and R_L (<1) shows better adsorption mechanism. Thermodynamics parameters- enthalpy change (ΔH°), entropy change (ΔS°) and the free energy (ΔG°) were, also, evaluated. The value of ΔG° was found to be negative at various constant temperatures, which confirms the feasibility and the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process. The value of ΔH° (42.84KJ/Kg) is positive, indicating that reaction was exothermic. Also, ΔS° (0.003KJ/KgK) was positive, illustrating the increasing randomness at the solid-liquid interface during the adsorption of solid particles onto the Cow Bone Granule (CBG) adsorbent.

KEYWORDS: Cow bone, adsorption, dissolved solids, isotherm, thermodynamics.

INTRODUCTION

Indiscriminate disposal of untreated industrial wastes into the environment is of global concern. Surface waters, including industrial wastewater, contain both dissolved and suspended particles. These particles vary considerably in source, composition, charge, particle size, shape and density. Appropriate applications of Adsorption process have been proved to be effective in the removal of dissolved particles in the effluent wastewaters (Kaushick, et al, 2007). The process transfers a constituent in the liquid phase to the solid phase. Though the adsorption process may not have been used extensively in wastewater treatment, demand for a better quality of treated wastewater effluent (including toxicity reduction) has led to an intensive examination and use of activated carbon in wastewater treatment. Adsorption of dyes from solutions has been extensively used for the determination of surface areas and examination of the accessibility of porous structures to dye molecules; and has become a standard practice in the qualitative evaluation of active carbons in the industry (Adham et al, 1996; Freeman et al, 1996). Amy and Cho (1999) reported that a portion of the mineral composition of coal (predominantly *pyrite* and *alkali metal* compounds) interacts with dye molecules, affecting the rate of adsorption. Careful selection of adsorbent (with respect to polarity, acidity, surface activity, molecular area in adsorbed state), adsorption from solutions could become a sensitive 'molecular probe' for investigation of coal effluent wastewater surfaces. In particular, adsorption from liquid phases appears to have the potential to become a useful tool for detecting changes in surface properties.

A range of adsorbents has been examined by different authors viz: sago waste, banana pith, cassava waste (Maiti, 2001), but a literature search reveals that interest is yet to capture the use of cow bone as adsorbent for the removal of dissolve particles from coal effluent sample has not been given recognition and this informed the present study. To this effect, an attempt was made to study the feasibility of cow bone granule- a cheap, easily available bio-sorbent for adsorption of dissolved solid particles from coal effluent. Equally, the use of Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms to access the fitness of the models to the batch adsorption data and thermodynamics of the process were, also, studied.

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES EMPLOYED DURING THE STUDY

(A) *Adsorption Isotherm*

The Carbon Adsorption Capacity is given by:

$$q_t = (x/m)C_o \quad (2)$$

The Freundlich isotherm is defined as follows:

$$x/m = K_f C_t^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where x/m = mass of adsorbate adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent (mg/g)

K_f = Freundlich capacity factor (l effluent/mg adsorbate)^{1/n}

C_t = concentration of adsorbate in solution after adsorption (mg/l)

$1/n$ = Freundlich intensity parameter.

Linearizing equation (3), we have:

$$\text{Log } (x/m) = \text{log } K_f + 1/n \text{ Log } C_t \quad (3a)$$

The constants in the Freundlich isotherm are determined by plotting $\text{Log}(x/m)$ versus $\text{Log}(C_t)$, where $\text{Log}(K_f)$ and $1/n$ are intercept and slope of the graph respectively.

Also, the Langmuir isotherm is defined by the following expression:

$$\frac{x}{m} = \frac{abC_t}{1 + bC_t} \quad (4)$$

Where,

x/m = mass of adsorbate adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent (mg/g)

a, b = empirical constants

C_t = concentration of adsorbate in solution after adsorption (mg/l).

Equation (4) can be rearranged as:

$$\frac{C_t}{x/m} = \frac{1}{ab} + \frac{1}{a} C_t \quad (4a)$$

(B) *Thermodynamics Parameters*

Similarly, the free energy of a thermodynamic system is given by:

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (5)$$

And

$$\text{Log } (q_t/C_t) = \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{2.303R} + \frac{-\Delta H^\circ}{2.303RT} \quad (6)$$

Where q_t = adsorption capacity (mg/g)

C_t = final concentration at time, t (mg/l)

R = gas constant (8.314Jmol/K)

T = temperature (K)

Thermodynamic parameters in equation (5) are in linear range of adsorption isotherm, and hence can be used with experimental data for their evaluations.

From plotting $\text{Log}(q_t/C_t)$ versus $(1/T)$ in equation (6), ΔH° and ΔS° may be evaluated, from which ΔG° can be calculated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Preparation of the Cow Bone Granule (CBG)

The cow bone was collected from a cow slaughter corner at Owerri in Imo State. It was extensively washed with running tap water, followed by washing with distilled water to remove dirt. The bone was then cut into smaller pieces and crushed in a blender. The sample was impregnated in a 60% strength orthophosphoric acid (within 24-hours) for activation, after which it was dried in an oven dryer. The sample was subjected to carbonization process at a charring temperature of 500°C, using a furnace equipment of model- 2KX0-60. A ceramic mortar set was used to grind the adsorbent sample, and a sieve size of 600µm was subsequently obtained, which gave the required granular size of the sample.

B. Batch Adsorption Process

Batch adsorption experiment was carried out at room temperature (25-30°C). In each experiment, 20ml of the coal effluent of known initial concentration (0.14mg/l) was treated with a specific amount (by weight) of the activated cow bone granule (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0g), at various contact time (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40 and 60mins). Ultra-Violet Spectrophotometer (UVS) equipment was used to determine both the initial and the final concentration of effluent sample.

The concentration of dissolved solid particles adsorbed, C was evaluated as follows:

$$C = C_o - C_t \tag{1}$$

Where,

C_o = Initial concentration of coal effluent (before treatment)

C_t = Final concentration of coal effluent at time, t

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Concentration-Time Behaviour and Adsorption Efficiency

It could be observed that particle concentration in the effluent reduces as contact time increases (Fig 1). This is traceable to the fact that as time proceeds, the point charge interactions between the cow bone granule and the solid particles in the wastewater sample increases, thereby increasing the rate of the adsorption process (Snoeyink and Summers, 1999). The efficiency plot (Fig 2) shows that the highest adsorbate removal (>60%) was recorded at the highest adsorbent mass (1.0g). This suggests that the number of available active sites increases with increase in the adsorbent mass, which results to reduced competition for adsorption sites, and the adsorption process readily increases; a similar observation was reported by Parkait and Dasgupta (2005) in the adsorption of Eosin dye on activated carbon.

Fig 1: Particle Concentration versus Time at Varying masses of CBG

Fig 2: Percentage Adsorption of Particle on CBG at Varying Masses

(B) Adsorption Isotherm

The concentration of solid particles removed from the coal effluent was evaluated using equation (1) and x/m (mg of adsorbate/g of adsorbent), as well as final concentration at various contact time, were calculated. The Freundlich Constants- K_f and $1/n$ were deduced from the plot of $\text{Log}(x/m)$ against $\text{Log}(C_t)$ of equation (2). Also, the plot of $C_t/(x/m)$ versus C_t of equation (4a) gave rise to the Langmuir constants - a and b . The correlation coefficients (R^2) for both isotherms were obtained using computer software (MS-Excel). The isotherm parameters are shown in Table 1, while the plots of the models are shown in figures 3 and 4 respectively. The values of $1/n$ and $R_L (<1)$ for Freundlich and Langmuir models respectively indicate favourable adsorption process (Table 1); smaller value of $1/n$ and R_L shows better adsorption mechanism and the formation of relatively strong bond between the adsorbate and the adsorbent (Kushwaha et al, 2003). The correlation coefficients for both isotherms, when compared, suggest that the Freundlich model fits the adsorption data better than the Langmuir model (R^2 for Freundlich isotherm = 0.996 > R^2 for Langmuir isotherm = 0.983).

Table 1: Isotherm Parameters for Freundlich and Langmuir Models

Freundlich Constants			Langmuir Constants			
$k_f(l/mg)$	$1/n$	R^2	a	b	R_L	R^2
82.43	0.4274	0.996	0.0017	1.6812	0.026	0.983

Fig 3: Freundlich Isotherm Plot

Fig 4: Langmuir Isotherm Plot

(C) *Thermodynamics Study*

The thermodynamic parameters (ΔG° , ΔH° , and ΔS°) were estimated using the relationship in equation (6), and are placed in Table 2; this is important to assess the feasibility and spontaneous nature of the adsorption process. The negative value of ΔG° confirms the feasibility of the process and the spontaneous nature of sorption. The values of ΔH° are positive, indicating that sorption is an endothermic process. The positive value of ΔS° illustrates the increasing randomness at the solid-liquid interface during the adsorption of solid particles onto the CBG adsorbent.

Table 2: Thermodynamics Parameters for the CBG Adsorbent

ΔH° (KJ/mol)	ΔS° (KJ/mol/K)	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (KJ/mol)		
		308K	313K	318K
41.84	0.003	76.28	73.81	51.94

CONCLUSION

This study has, once more, proved that the use of adsorption techniques for the removal of dissolved solid particles from effluent wastewater samples is very effective and reliable. The concentration of particles removed from the coal effluent increases with time. Rate of adsorption is higher when higher adsorbent mass is fed. Both Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms fitted the batch adsorption data. The adsorption process was endothermic, feasible and spontaneous, and proceeded in the direction of increasing randomness at the solid-liquid interface.

REFERENCES

Aharoni, C., and M. Ungarish (1977) Kinetics of Activated Chemisorption- Theoretical Models. *Faraday Trans 1*(73), pp 456-464.

Benjamin, M.M. (2001); *Water Chemistry*. McGraw-Hill Company Ltd, New York.

Dick, R.I. and B.B. Ewing (1997) Evaluation of Activated Sludge Thickening Theories. *Journal of American Society of Civil Engineers*. 93(4), pp 41-53.

Government of Jordan (1995) *Jordanian Standards for Water Re-use*, JS-893/995. Standard Publishers. Amman, Jordan. pp 36-37.

John L. Rose (2001) *Advance Waste Treatment of Secondary Effluent with Activated Carbon*. Burns and Roe Inc., New Jersey. pp 43-50.

Karabulut, S. (2000) Batch Removal of Copper (II) from Aqueous Solutions with Low Rank Turkish Coals. *Journal of Purification Technology*, 18(10), pp 177-188.

Kashik, K.K. (2007) Physiochemical Parameters, Isotherms, Sorption Kinetics and Column Operations for Adsorption of Copper (II) from Wastewater Using Fly Ash, *Journal of Applied Sciences*, 66(11), pp 170-177.

Maiti, S.K. (2001) Handbook of Methods in Environmental Studies, Vol. 1-ABD Publishers, Jaipur. India.

Marshal, W.E. and C.A. Toles (2002) Copper Ion Removal by Almond Shell Carbons and Commercial Carbons: Batch and Column Studies. *Journal of Science and Technology*. 37(84), pp 2369-2383.

Metcalf and Eddy (2003) Wastewater Engineering-Treatment and Re-use, 4th ed. McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd, New-York.

Rose, J.B. and C.P. Garba (1991) Assessing Potential Health Risks from Viruses and Parasites in Reclaimed Water, In: *Water Science Technology. Journal of U.S. EIA*, 23(4), pp 470-493.

Sawyer, C.N. and G.F. Parkin (1994) Chemistry for Environmental Engineering, 4th ed. McGraw-Hill Company Ltd, New York.

Shilpi, Kushwaha (2003) Equilibrium, kinetics and Thermodynamic Studies for Adsorption of Hg (II) on Palm Shell Powder. *Journal of World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, 43(4), pp 600-605.

Tchobanoglous, G and E.D. Shroeder (1985) Water Quality: Characteristics, Modeling and Modification. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, Reading-MA.

U.S. EPA (2001) Proposed Rule for Protection of Communities from Over-Flowing Sewers. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 625-R-92-013 (Revised). Washington D C.

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